

Local Government in Malaysia

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments

5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Malaysia: An Introduction

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Careful perusal of the text of the Federal Constitution would indicate that the intention was to provide only a measure of real autonomy for state governments from the federal government, and that local authorities also enjoy autonomy from state and federal governments, albeit less than that enjoyed by state governments. However, such reading would obscure the fact that very little such autonomy exists in practice. The centralised nature of the federation is well established in analyses in the literature (Malaysia is often referred to as a ‘quasi-federation’ rather than a real federation, or as truly federal only with regard to Sabah and Sarawak, not the states of Peninsular Malaysia).⁶⁴ As a result the government system is in practice far more centralised than Southeast Asia’s unitary states, such as Thailand, Indonesia and the Philippines. Much the same may be said of local government, which has even less say than state governments in inter-governmental relations (IGR). This situation is due to a number of factors, mentioned earlier, which are now examined in turn in more detail.

Dominant-party System and Patronage-based Politics

IGR involving local government in Malaysia are rendered more complex than a mere statement of constitutional and administrative law might indicate, due to the operation (historically speaking) of the dominant-party system under the Barisan Nasional (formerly Alliance) (BN) government (1957-2018). For almost all of this period and in almost all states, at least up until 2008, when the federal opposition coalition won several state governments, appointees at federal, state and local government levels were appointed from within the BN power structure. This meant that state *Menteri Besar* (chief ministers) were in effect appointed by the Prime Minister; state executive councils (equivalent of the cabinet at federal level) were appointed by *Menteri Besar*; and local councillors were appointed by the state government almost exclusively from the ranks of party members. In this system IGR were therefore in large part a matter of intra-party (not even inter-party, except for BN component parties) relations. A good example of the effects of the political process on local government is provided in the case study of the SPICE controversy⁶⁵ in Penang. This shows that what is described here is not at all confined to the BN and its component parties, but is taken as a norm even by parties that have been in opposition to the BN and are now in power in some states.

⁶⁴ Andrew Harding, *The Constitution of Malaysia: A Contextual Analysis* (2nd edn, Hart/Bloomsbury, forthcoming 2022) Chapter 6.

⁶⁵ See report section 5.2. on the SPICE Controversy in the section on intergovernmental relations of local governments in Malaysia.

The National Council for Local Government

The National Council for Local Government (NCLG) is a body established under Article 95A of the Constitution in 1960 that makes national policies for the promotion, development and control of local governments, and in effect controls the kinds of laws and policies that the states can make on local government.⁶⁶ The state governments must follow the policies made by the NCLG. For example, when the state governments of Selangor and Penang (then held by federal opposition parties) requested the Election Commission (EC) to conduct local government elections, the EC held (it is suggested, incorrectly) that NCLG's agreement was necessary.⁶⁷

The NCLG consists of a federal minister as chairman (normally the Prime Minister), and one representative from each of the states (normally the Chief Minister) appointed by the Ruler (or Governor, on government advice); and generally no more than 10 representatives of the federal government. Given this composition, the NCLG is without doubt highly influential, and the Prime Minister, normally chairing the meetings, determines its agenda and direction.⁶⁸ Ultimately, the NCLG's agenda and interests reflect those of the federal government.⁶⁹ For this reason, the NCLG is considered by some to be quite improper in a federal system, as it can be said to trespass on states' rights, which include powers in respect of local government. Since the NCLG is legitimised by a constitutional amendment introducing Article 95A, it can only be argued that it is an unconstitutional body by relying on the 'basic structure' doctrine, which has a hold, but a tenuous hold, in Malaysian case law.⁷⁰

The setting up of the NCLG is considered to be part of the extensive local government reforms that took place between its establishment in 1960 and 1988. It was established under Article 95A to coordinate policies and laws between the federal, state and local spheres of government, such that uniformity of local government laws and policies in Malaysia could be achieved. Article 95A provides that after consultation with state governments the NCLG can 'formulate policies for the promotion, development, control of local government throughout the federation and for the administration of any laws relating thereto'.⁷¹

A Penang state assemblyman, Gooi Hsiao Leung, reflecting widely-held opinion, stated that the state governments could become more effective if there were a decentralisation of power

⁶⁶ See Art 95A, and also Art 76 of the Federal Constitution, which provides for the federal legislature to make laws for the purpose of uniformity between states.

⁶⁷ Danesh Prakash Chacko, *Reintroduction of Local Government Elections in Malaysia* (Bersih & Adil Network Sdn Bhd. 2021).

⁶⁸ Tricia Yeoh, *Federal-State Relations under the Pakatan Harapan Government* (ISEAS Publishing 2020).

⁶⁹ Kai Ostwald, 'Federalism without Decentralization: Power Consolidation in Malaysia' (2017) 43 *Journal of Southeast Asian Economies* 488.

⁷⁰ Wilson Tay, 'Basic Structure Revisited: The Case of *Seminyeh Jaya* and the Defence of Fundamental Constitutional Principles in Malaysia' (2019) 14 *Asian Journal of Comparative Law* 113.

⁷¹ Phang Siew Noi, *Decentralisation or Recentralisation? Trends in Local Government in Malaysia* (University of Malaya 2008).

from the federal government: ‘It will be better for Penang as we are in the best position to know what is needed for our state instead of bureaucrats stationed far away in Putrajaya’. An example he provided was that ‘even when the state government wants to reinstate the Penang Voluntary Patrol Team (PPS), it cannot be done without federal approval’. In fact the PPS was held by the Court of Appeal to be constitutionally within state powers.⁷² Gooi also pointed out that federal funds were being distributed unfavourably to the states: ‘Penang received only 3 per cent of the tax revenue collected from the state between 2001 and 2008’. He reported that the budgets of all 13 states in Malaysia combined were equivalent to only 6 per cent of the federal budget in 2013 and the was figure reduced by 0.2 per cent in 2018.⁷³

Although local government policy is formulated by the NCLG in consultation with federal and state governments, the political system as outlined above means that the federal government gets its way, and local authorities are – astonishingly – not represented at all in a process designed to serve their needs. There is a Malaysian Association of Local Authorities⁷⁴ which could easily represent them in such policy deliberations.

The Public Service

The public service (equivalent to the ‘civil service’ in some systems) is organized via the Public Service Commission (PSC) at the federal level, serving both federal and state governments, but not local government, which employs its own staff. This system works to the disadvantage of local government and to IGR in two respects.

First, the PSC provides consistent standards and rules for recruitment, pay, promotion, and transfer between governments. Local government staff do not have these advantages, and tend to get stuck in terms of advancement due to lack of opportunity. This decreases morale and commitment.

Secondly, local government does not, as a result, benefit from integration of public service that would render smooth and highly professional the system of IGR across federal, state and local governments.

The argument is often heard that deficiencies in staffing, and especially in technical expertise, make decentralisation at the local government level a risky enterprise. This of course is an outcome of the system of public employment, not a necessary consequence of having local government or subsidiarity per se. Subject to democratic controls, adequately funded, and linked to the PSC, there is no reason to suppose that local authorities would not perform very well, as they did during the first ten years after independence.

⁷² *Government of the State of Penang v Minister for Home Affairs & others* [2017] 4 MLJ 770.

⁷³ ‘Backbencher Wants more Autonomy for Penang’ (*Malay Mail*, 11 December 2018) <<https://www.malaymail.com/news/malaysia/2018/11/12/backbencher-wants-more-autonomy-for-penang/1692628>>.

⁷⁴ See the association’s website, <www.mala.com.my>.

Powers of State Governments

As was stated earlier, state governments are also empowered under the LGA to give general directions to local governments. In addition, local council budgets must be submitted to the state government for approval not later than 20 November in each year;⁷⁵ and the raising of loans by local governments is subject to the consent of the state government.⁷⁶ Furthermore, all local government by-laws, rules, and regulations are subject to state government approval;⁷⁷ as are annual assessments, drainage rates and valuation lists.⁷⁸

State governments also exert some control over local governments' exercise of planning powers. States are governed planning-wise by a system of structure plans under the Town and Country Planning Act 1976 (TCPA), while local plans are drawn up by local governments.⁷⁹ The latter are still nonetheless subject to approval by the state government. Oddly enough, though, the TCPA allows local governments to make rules regarding regulation of land development, classes of use, and regulation of height, design, appearance of buildings and density of developments; and these rules *prevail* over state government rules if they conflict. This is one of few areas where local governments can go against the wishes of the state government.

It is therefore not too much of an exaggeration to say that IGR in Malaysia present a highly centralised system of government in which local governments exercise comparatively little discretion as to policy and even sometimes with regard to particular decisions, as seen in the SPICE case study below.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Harding A, 'Local Democracy in a Multi-Layered Constitutional System: Malaysian Local Government Reconsidered' in Andrew Harding and Mark Sidel (eds), *Central-Local Relations in Asian Constitutional Systems* (Hart Publishing 2015)

Phang Siew Noi, *Decentralisation or Recentralisation? Trends in Local Government in Malaysia* (University of Malaya 2008)

Yeoh T, *Federal-State Relations under the Pakatan Harapan Government* (ISEAS Publishing 2020)

⁷⁵ Local Government Act 1976 (LGA), Sec 55.

⁷⁶ Sec 40.

⁷⁷ Sec 103.

⁷⁸ Secs 127, 128, 143.

⁷⁹ For more information on this, see report section 6 on people's participation in local decision-making in Malaysia.

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